
**USERS SATISFACTION WITH ICT-BASED RESOURCES AND SERVICES IN
MANAGEMENT INSTITUTIONS LIBRARIES: A STUDY OF INSTITUTE OF
PROFESSIONAL STUDIES MBA COLLEGE LIBRARY, PUNE**

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Abstract:

Libraries at management institutions are quickly moving away from the old methods of providing library services in favor of resources and services based on information and communication technology (ICT). Without integrating ICT into its regular services, no library can adequately meet the information demands of its many patrons. This study examined the degree of user satisfaction with ICT-based resources and services at the IPS MBA College Library in Pune on the basis of these premises. A structured questionnaire created following a thorough evaluation of relevant literature served as the instrument for data collection in the study's descriptive survey research design. All first-year and second-year students who enrolled with the MBA College Library for the 2019–21 academic years made up the 480 person population. 250 library patrons made up the sample (200 first-year students and 50 second-year students) the gathered data was examined using percentages and statistical means. The results showed that students in the IPS MBA College were happy with the use of ICT-based resources and services, notably the usage of online database resources, to suit their information needs in the university library. Therefore, it was advised that the Institute Library Management should put in greater effort to enhance the current ICT-based resources and services that are accessible for use in the library.

Keywords: User Satisfaction, ICT Resources, ICT Services, Management Libraries, Library Users

Introduction:

Ijiekhuamhen, Aghojare, and Omosekejimi (2015) defined satisfaction of library users' information requirements as the extent to which the users' information needs are satisfied and the degree to which their satisfaction increases their continued use of the library resources and services. Every contemporary library's first priority is to meet the information demands of its patrons. No matter how much effort it takes, librarians and information specialists will always try to meet the information needs of every

library customer. In order to meet the information demands of library patrons, information and communication technologies (ICTs) have been integrated into the daily operations of 21st-century libraries. Libraries and information centers have continued to employ ICT in recent years to meet the various information demands of its patrons, as Haneefa (2007) puts it. The definition of a library is an organization whose primary goal is to collect, arrange, maintain, and make quickly accessible to users all types of information resources they need (Nwalo,

2003). According to Kavitha (2001), who was referenced by Sivakumaren, Geetha, and Jeyaprakash (2011), libraries have always used the most up-to-date technology to serve their patrons. ICT has consequently evolved in the present to become a force that has enhanced and transformed the delivery of library services. ICTs have developed into highly significant tools for engaging in the global market, boosting educational activities, improving the delivery of basic services, and enhancing local development chances, according to Tella (2003) as referenced by Aiyebilehin (2012). According to Ajaegbu, Ehioghae, and Oreoluwa (2014), computers and their peripherals, internet connectivity, the Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC), fax machines, scanners, and electronic maps are all examples of ICT-based library resources that modern libraries use to provide their services. E-journals, CD-ROM databases, online databases, e-books, and a variety of other electronic media are quickly replacing the traditional library resources, according to Kumar (2012). ICT-based services are ones that are provided in libraries utilising all forms of technology to replace more conventional services. The development of ICT has led to the creation of electronic information in the form of e-books, e-journals, online databases, and the Internet, ushering in a new era of information.

The practice of the library and information profession has undergone a complete transformation since the emergence of ICT. ICT has surely led to a surge of innovations in the delivery of library services. It is no secret that ICT has a significant influence on library services. The impact on Nigeria's social and economic development is discussed in EfosaEgharevbaCJLIS (2018) 1(1) 51–62.

Without integrating ICT into its regular services, no library can adequately meet the information demands of its many patrons. ICT has a significant impact on many facets of modern life, including trade, health, education, and entertainment. The library is unquestionably a component of this ICT influence. The Internet allows for the more effective and efficient delivery of library services. For instance, questions from library users are answered quickly, and reference services that were formerly provided face-to-face between the library customers and the Reference staff are now provided online. Since becoming digital, librarians are now referred to as e-reference services. For librarians and information professionals, user satisfaction with ICT-based resources and services is of the highest significance. Users' satisfaction with ICT-based resources and services varies to varying degrees. ICT-based services are those provided in libraries that use every type of technology now in use in place of more conventional services. The development of ICT has led to the creation of electronic information in the form of e-books, e-journals, online databases, and the Internet, ushering in a new era of information.

Objective:

- 1) Identify users are getting satisfaction from the ICT-based resources and services available in the library.
- 2) find out the level of users' satisfaction with accessibility to the Internet of MBA Library.
- 3) Understand what the level of users' satisfaction with e-reference services in college Libraries.

Hypothesis:

- 1) Users' satisfaction with ICT-based resources and services varied to varying degrees.
- 2) The level of users' satisfaction with accessibility to the Internet of MBA Library is very good.
- 3) Librarians provide quick and easy e-reference service to their users.

Research Methodology:

The descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. All first-year and second-year students who enrolled with the MBA College Library for the 2019–21 academic years made up the 480 person population. 250 library patrons made up the sample (200 first-year students and 50 second-year students) the gathered data was examined using percentages and statistical means. The tool used to gather the data was a structured questionnaire that was validated by a senior librarian in the library of the IPS MBA Institute College after being developed following a thorough examination of the relevant literature. There were two sections to the questionnaire. While part 2 was tasked with answering questions on users' levels of satisfaction with ICT-based resources and services in the IPS MBA Library, section 1 contained replies to questions about the demographic information of respondents. 250 copies of the questionnaire were administered randomly to the respondents, while 240 copies were returned. Out of the 240 copies of questionnaire returned, 194 were from first year students while 46 were from second year students.

Literature Review:

Online database resources are dominating academic research information

activities, and researchers have recognized the value of these resources and are utilizing them, claim Edem and Egbe (2016).

According to Hussain, Khan, and Zaidi (2013), and Idiegbeyan-ose and Ilo (2013), ICT services provided in the library are those that are provided utilizing a mix of ICT resources to suit users' information requirements.

Knowledge and communication technologies (ICTs) have completely changed how people live and work, especially in terms of how quickly and widely information can now be produced, shared, and recycled—of which the library is the most important example. "The concept of information and communication technology (ICT) in the library encompasses the gathering (acquisition), organisation (packaging), storage, retrieval, and dissemination of information resources that can be in textual or numerical (books, documents), pictorial and vocal forms (audio-visual), or a combination of all of the above (multimedia)" (Lawal–Solarin, 2013).

Broadband internet connection is a necessary ICT service for the library, according to Muhammad and Garko (2012), as it enhances information flow and facilitates idea sharing and exchange between library patrons and librarians.

Online databases, according to Ukpabor (2012), offer precise and timely academic information, particularly for students who heavily rely on them for information to develop their study and collaborate with other scholars across the world for intellectual advancement.

In their list of additional ICT resources, Muhammad and Garko (2012) also included the middleware, storage, and computer hardware and accessories needed to produce, access, save, transfer, and alter

information on the information superhighway.

Information commons are also included in Dhanavandan, Esmail, and Nagarajan's (2012) list of ICT services provided by the library. The term "information commons" refers to a collection of network access points and related ICT resources that are arranged to facilitate learning in the context of physical, digital, human, and social resources. ICT-based services are those that were formerly offered to library patrons in person but are now provided electronically both online and offline via the use of computers and Internet services.

ICT is a general phrase that refers to any technological and communication tools used in teaching and learning. A computer system, communication tool, telecommunication, phone, satellite, telex, facsimile, internet, e-mail, fax, video text, and document delivery, electronic copiers, radio, and television are only a few examples of such a technology, according to Sivakumaren, Geetha, and Jeyaprakash (2011).

According to Okewale and Adetimirin (2011), ICT has significantly improved how information is maintained in libraries. Due to the advancement of ICT, information has undergone changes. Quick and simple access to all necessary information is crucial, especially in academic libraries. Information and communication technology (ICT)-based resources are those that are used to gather, organize, store, and distribute information electronically.

Ekoja (2011) said that the web 2.0, which permits the use of social media

technologies to deliver ICT services, is one highly significant ICT-based service.

ICT resources or equipment, according to Ohonba (2010), offer ways to gather, store, encode, process, analyze, send, receive, and disseminate (text, audio, or video) information. ICT resources are therefore those that are utilized in libraries to help the electronic information storage, organization, and distribution. When accessing online database resources, ICT tools or resources are used with the assistance of the internet, which has become a crucial component in meeting consumers' information demands.

Isah (2010) asserts that the development of ICT has accelerated the availability and use of electronic resources in contemporary society. These ICT resources are computer-based resources that help with information storage, retrieval, and distribution.

ICT resources are classified as computer hardware and software by Haneefa (2007) and consist of computer systems, printers, scanners, floppy discs, magnetic tape, CD ROMs, DVDs, VCDs, smart cards, telephones, fax machines, telnet servers, e-journals, e-books, and OPAC.

According to Olakule (2007), these ICT services also make it easier to educate and learn by connecting hospitals, residences, companies, and schools.

Libraries without access to ICT in this As most students, teachers, and researchers are aware of the benefits the internet offers and turn to cybercafés at a significantly higher cost to meet their current information demands, the 21st century may no longer be relevant to the academic community (Ajala, 2007).

Result:**Results Table 1: Percentage Distribution of Types of ICT-based Resources (N = 240)**

S/N	ICT Based Resources used by library users in meeting information needs	Used		Not Used	
		Frequency	Percentage (%)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	CD-ROM databases	211	87.9	29	12.1
2	Online database resources	238	99.2	2	0.8
3	E-books	236	98.3	4	1.7
4	E-journals	217	90.4	23	9.6
5	Computers	238	99.2	2	0.8
6	Scanners	236	98.3	4	1.7
7	Printers	238	99.2	2	0.8

Table 1 listed the numerous ICT-based resources employed in the IPS MBA Library to satiate users' informational demands. The CD ROM databases are the

least utilized ICT-based resources. It was clear from this that all of the ICT-based resources listed in Table 1 are employed to satisfy users' information demands.

Table 2: Percentage Distribution of Types of ICT-based Services (N = 240).

S/N	ICT Based Resources used by library users in meeting information needs	Used		Not Used	
		Frequency	Percentage (%)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Digital reference services	199	82.9	41	17.1
2	Internet services	240	100.0	0	0.0
3	E-mail services	157	65.4	83	34.6
4	Social media services	158	65.8	82	34.2

Table 2 listed the ICT-based services offered by the IPS MBA Library. The findings showed that all respondents 100% said they could access the internet.

Email and social networking services, meanwhile, are only sporadically accessible.

Table 3: Mean Rating of Level of Users' Satisfaction with Online Database Resources (N = 240).

S/N	Online Database Resources	Mean	SD
1	KNIMBUS DIGITAL LIBRARY	4.51	.68
2	DELNET	4.38	.73
3	J-GATE	4.38	.78
4	EBSCOHOST	3.91	.70
5	NDL	3.98	.79

Table 3 the satisfaction with the IPS MBA library's online database resources was shown in this table. The outcome showed that items 1 through 5 are above the criteria mean, with Knimbus

Digital Library having the highest mean of 4.51 and being item 1. Users are generally satisfied with the availability of online database resources.

Table 4: Mean Rating of the Level of Users' Satisfaction with Accessibility to the Internet (N = 240).

S/N	Accessibility to the Internet	Mean	SD
1	There is easy accessibility to internet facilities	4.42	.56
2	There is strong and functional internet access	4.34	.56
3	There is uninterrupted internet connectivity access	4.13	.82
4	The internet access and browsing is very fast	4.28	.77
5	The internet Wi-Fi is accessible from any location in the library	3.97	.84

Table 4 shown the degree of customers' satisfaction with the IPS MBA Library's Internet accessibility. All of the items were ranked higher than the criteria

mean, with Item 1 having the highest mean ($x = 4.42$), according to the results. As a result, users' satisfaction with internet accessibility is satisfactory.

Table 5: Mean Rating of the Level of Users' Satisfaction with E-reference Services (N = 240).

S/N	Users' satisfaction with e-reference Services	Mean	SD
1	When carrying out Project work	4.18	.67
2	When receiving information on new library policy	3.57	.76
3	When sending query to reference librarian on library matters	3.42	.84
4	For general communication with reference librarian	4.09	.75
5	For receiving SMS alert on new arrivals in the library	3.13	.86

Table 5 displayed the degree of user satisfaction with the e-reference services provided by the IPS MBA Library. All of the items were ranked

higher than the criteria mean, with Item 1 having the highest mean (4.18). As a result, users are satisfied with the level of e-reference services.

Conclusion:

We may conclude that practically all ICT-based resources are used by IPS MBA Library users to fulfill their informational demands. Students at the IPS MBA Institute in Pune use computers, scanners, printers, e-books, e-journals, CD-ROM databases, and online database resources to suit their information demands. This research paper supports the idea that management library users employ ICT-based resources to fulfill their information demands in management libraries. The Internet service is the most easily accessible to library patrons of all the ICT-based services offered at the IPS MBA Library, according to additional research findings. The rate at which management-level library users rely on the internet for free electronic resources shows in his study that the management library's Internet services are beneficial to users, as

none of the respondents cited a lack of internet access as a barrier to using e-library services. Users of the library use the online database resources' platforms, including OPAC, DIGITAL SOFTWARE, NDLI, J-GATE, EBSCOHOST, DELNET, and KNIMBUS DIGITAL LIBRARY, to meet their information needs. The outcomes also showed that IPS MBA Library's e-reference services are well-liked by its users. Users of the IPS MBA library use the e-reference services when conducting research, corresponding with the reference librarian in general, receiving SMS alerts of new arrivals in the library, contacting the reference librarian with questions about the library, and learning about new library policies.

It is clear from the analysis and discussion of the study's findings that library users, particularly students at IPS Institute in Pune, utilize all ICT-based

resources and services provided by the college library to meet their information needs, and that they are satisfied with the level of accessibility to the Internet. The user's satisfaction with the usage of online database resources and e-reference services is further increased by the internet's accessibility. In general, user's at the IPS MBA library in Pune are satisfied with the ICT-based materials and services.

Recommendations:

The following suggestions are still practical even if there appears to be a decently good level with the utilization of ICT-based resources and services from the research:

- 1) IPS MBA library's management should come up with ways to find out how satisfied its users are with its ICT-based materials and services. This will aid them in developing their strategies, strengthening their strengths, and enhancing their weaknesses.
- 2) Additionally, additional efforts should be made to raise awareness of the IPS MBA Library Management's users' ICT-based services provided to students and the availability of online database resources at the library, particularly during students' orientation.
- 3) In order to boost library users' happiness with their access to other ICT services, Internet access in the IPS MBA Library should be substantially enhanced. This is so because the majority of ICT-based services provided in libraries depend on the usability and accessibility of the Internet.
- 4) The management of the IPS MBA Library should exert more effort to enhance the current ICT-based resources and services accessible in the

library in order to raise the degree of satisfaction with these ICT resources and services in the library.

References:

- 1) Ajala, I. O. (2007). Internet awareness, accessibility and use by undergraduate and postgraduate students in Nigeria universities: a case study of LAUTECH, Ogbomoso, Nigeria. *The Information Technologist*, 4(2), 147 – 162.
- 2) Dhanavandan, S., Esmail, S. M. &Nagarajan, M. (2012). Access and awareness of ICT resources and services in medical college libraries in Puducherry. *Library Philosophy and Practice (ejournal)*, paper 750. Retrieved from <http://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/750>
- 3) Edem, N. B. &Egbe, N. G. (2016). Availability and utilization of electronic resources by postgraduate students in a Nigerian university library: a case study of University of Calabar, Nigeria. *Information and Knowledge Management*, 6(2), 61 – 69. Retrieved from www.iiste.org
- 4) Egharevba, Efosa . (2018). Users' Satisfaction with ICT-Based Resources and Services in University Libraries: A study of Igbinedion University Library, Okada, Edo State, Nigeria. *Covenant Journal of Library and Information Science*, 1(1),52-54.
- 5) Ekoja, I. I. (2011). Modern ICT tools: online electronic resources sharing using web 2.0 and its implication for library and information practice in Nigeria. *Samaru Journal of Information Studies*, 11(1&2), 53 – 58
- 6) Gaikwad, M.N. (2017). Awareness and use of electronic information resources at arts and

- commerce college
Madha: A Study. J. Adv. Library & Information Science, 6(4): 329-333. Retrieved from <http://jalis.in/pdf/6-4/Gaik.pdf>
- 7) Haneefa, K. M. (2007). Use of ICT based resources and services in special libraries in Kerala. *Annals of Library and Information Studies*, 54, 23 – 32.
- 8) Hase, V. L., & Gaikwad, M. N. (2021). Online Databases Backbone for Teaching and Research: Case Study of Rajarambapu Institute of Technology, affiliated to Shivaji University, Kolhapur, Maharashtra (India). Retrieved from <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/6873/>
- 9) Hussain, A., Khan, M. A. & Zaidi, N. F. (2013). The ICT based library and information services: a case study of BSchools in Delhi and NCR region. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*, paper 1011. Retrieved from <http://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/1011>
- 10) Isah, A. (2010). Electronic library use by academic staff at the University of Ilorin, Nigeria. *Journal of Library and Information Science*, 7(1&2), 138 – 149
- 11) Lawal–Solarin, E. O. (2013). The Use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in academic libraries in Nigeria: a case study of Covenant University Library Ota, Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*. Retrieved from <http://unllib.unl.edu/LP>
- 12) Muhammad, M. & Garko, A. B. (2012). Information and Communication Technology (ICT): a tool for good governance. In M. Muhammad, A. B. Garko & M. T. Yakasai. (Eds.), *Advances in Information & Communication Technologies*, (pp. 136 – 153). Zaria: Ahmadu Bello University Press.
- 13) Ohonba, A. A. (2010). Computer networking at a glance. Benin City: Ambik Press.
- 14) Okewale, O. & Adetimirin, A. (2011). Information use of software packages in Nigerian university libraries. *Journal of Information Technology Impact*, 11(3), 211 – 224.
- 15) Olakule, F. K. (2007). Information and Communication Technologies in teacher training and professional development in Nigeria. *Turkish Online Journal of Distance Education*, 1(9), 133 – 139
- 16) Sivakumaren, K. S., Geetha, V. & Jeyaprakash, B. (2011). ICT facilities in university libraries: a study. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*. Retrieved from <http://unllib.unl.edu/LPP>
- 17) Ukpebor, C.O. (2012). Availability and use of electronic resources in African universities: The Nigerian perspective. *PNLA Quarterly*, 76(3) (Spring 2012) 190 – 199. Retrieved from www.pnla.org.